

ASSESSING EL LEARNERS: HOW TO ASSESS SPEAKING

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The article is about assessing English Language learners during the speaking process. Here the authors show the importance of assessing our students speaking abilities both in class and in formal speaking exam. At the same time they show some of the things the teachers do in order to ensure valid and reliable speaking assessment. The authors introduce speaking ways of assessing, including speaking categories of oral skills, special issues in speaking assessment and a range of assessment tasks.

Keywords: assessment, accuracy, fluency, speaking exams, communication.

As in daily life, speaking is an important channel of communication in a general English program. When testing this skill, we want to simulate real life situations in which students engage in conversation, ask and answer questions, and give information. In an academic English program, the emphasis may shift to participating in class discussions and debates or giving academic presentations. In a business English course, students might develop telephone skills, make reports, and interact to common situations involving meetings, travel, and sales. Whatever the teaching focus, valid assessment should reflect the course objectives.

We know the importance most students place on being able to speak proficiently, so we assess our students speaking abilities both in class and in formal speaking exam. Some of the things we do in order to ensure valid and reliable speaking assessment are:

- We start any speaking assessment with an unassessed warm-up to reduce nervousness
- We conduct our speaking exams with another teacher so that each has a specific role
- We use a range of assessment tasks
- We focus on both fluency and accuracy when marking students speech
- We record exams so that we have a record of them for later reference
- We limit the number of speaking exams per day to ensure intra-rater reliability
- We conduct regular calibration sessions with other teachers to ensure inter-rater reliability.

Heaton points out that speaking is “an extremely difficult skill to test, as it is far too complex a skill to permit any reliable analysis to be made for the purpose of objective testing”. [1, p. 112] The greater challenges are resource requirements and reliability, including the perceived subjectivity in grading. Lack of time, number of students, lack of available tests, and administrative difficulties are other pressing concerns. In addition, practicality issues for reliability of the marking often arise as raters must be trained, and this training can be very time consuming. For all these reasons, many teachers do not even attempt to assess speaking. However,

the assessment of spoken language has evolved dramatically over the last several decades from tests of oral grammar and pronunciation to tests of genuine communication, and now to integrative speaking tasks on high-stakes tests like the TOEFL and TOEIC.

Speaking is a complex skill requiring the simultaneous use of different abilities that often develop at different rates—namely pronunciation, grammar, vocabulary, fluency and comprehension. These abilities still underlie the assessment of speaking, but not more attention is paid to contextual and interactional factors.

Canale and Swain argue there are four competencies underlying speaking ability:

*Grammatical competence: includes knowledge of grammar, vocabulary and mechanics

*Discourse competence: concerned with relationships beyond the sentence level, rules of cohesion and coherence, holding communication together in a meaningful way

*Sociolinguistic competence: applying knowledge of what is expected socially and culturally by users of the target language

*Strategic competence: “the way learners manipulate language in order to meet communicative goals” [2, p. 228] the ability to know when to take the floor, how to keep a conversation going or end it, and how to resolve communication breakdowns.

Categories of Oral Skills

We categorise oral skills as speaking skills that are part of a repertoire of routines for exchanging information or interacting, and improvisational skills such as negotiating meaning and managing the interaction. The routine skills are largely associated with language functions and the spoken language required in certain situations like ordering food in a restaurant or asking for directions to a museum. By contrast, the improvisational skills are more general and may be brought into play at any time for clarification, to keep a conversation flowing, to change topics, or to take turns. It is the teachers task to decide which speaking skills are most germane to a particular program and then create a variety of assessment tasks. It is also common to weight some skills more heavily than others.

Before we focus specially on assessing speaking, it is necessary to understand some of the differences between the two productive language skills- writing and speaking. We have already seen that subjectivity is a

major issue in grading writing and that is also the case for assessing speaking. As with writing, there is the issue of whether to grade speaking holistically or analytically. [3, 201]

Writing	Speaking
Full, complex, and well-organized sentences	Incomplete, simply and loosely organized sentences
Information densely packed	Simpler discourse with less information
Use of specific vocabulary	Use of more general vocabulary
Use of discourse markers to help the reader	Frequent use of fillers to facilitate speech
Text written for an unseen audience	Face-to-face communication
A relatively solitary process	Negotiation of meaning between two or more people
Alterations and crossings out kept to a minimum	Alterations, corrections, and miscues are very common
Reference can easily be made to what has been written previously	Memory limitations are important as speech is transitory

These differences are fundamental to our understanding of the construct of speaking and any assessment of this skill must take these features into consideration.

In contrast to writing, speaking is more ephemeral unless measures are taken to record student performance. Yet the presence of recording equipment can negatively influence students performance and often recording is not practical or feasible.

Special Issues in Speaking Assessment

Logistically, the administration of speaking exams to large numbers of students can be overwhelming in terms of time and resources. With large classes, it is unrealistic to test speaking individually. For example, to test a class of 30 students individually, it would take more than four class periods to administer a 10-to 15-minute speaking exam. One solution is to develop assessments that test more than one student at a time, yet allow each student some opportunities to speak individually. Another solution is to test, formally only a few times during a course but to use continuous assessment of students during normal classroom activities.

Another phenomenon in speaking assessment is that sometimes a student can score higher on exams because of having an outgoing personality. Take care to evaluate a student on what was said in the exam, not on personality.

A number of factors need to be considered before designing speaking assessments. One is whether to focus more on fluency or accuracy. On the one hand, fluency is important for students, but if there are many errors, that might impede comprehension. We recommended that you focus equality on fluency and accuracy. Ask yourself whether the mistakes students make impede comprehension or cause a breakdown in communication. If they do not, ignore or play down the problems. One way to ensure that you place an equal focus on both fluency and accuracy is to build this into your assessment criteria. In other words, 50 percent of a student's grade would come from aspects of fluency

such as initiating and maintaining communication and 5- percent would be based on how accurately the student spoke.

Teachers also have to decide on which criteria to evaluate. If you expouse an equal emphasis on fluency and accuracy, we recommend the following marking categories; accuracy (grammar), vocabulary, linguistic ability (pronunciation, intonation and stress).

Another factor to consider before you design your assessment is the procedure for grading. Since subjectivity is a major problem in marking speaking exams, a common solution is to use multiple raters. The more teachers you use, the more reliable a test score will be. It is common practice to use two raters with different roles for speaking exams. One teacher, the interlocutor, interacts with the student or students being tested. The other teacher, the assessor, focuses on writing scores.

Debate on a controversial Topic

A debate is a formal public speaking activity where two students or groups of students argue for or against a topic. The topic they debate is called the motion. The student who argues for the motion usually starts the debate with a three-minute speech. The student on the opposing team then has a chance to argue against or rebut the arguments made by the first student. Group or team debates in which two teams of four students argue for and against a certain motion are preferred. Three students on each team deliver oral arguments. The remaining student serves as a silent observer who helps formulate the arguments or rebuttal statements.

Sample debate topics:

*Cigarette smoking should be banned in all public places.

*The legal driving age should be raised to 21.

*Men and women can never be just friends.

Here is a sample grading form for three students, each of whom is graded individually before a group grade is given.

Grading chat for Three-Student Debate

The motion

Content	Mark	Speaker 1 Names:	Speaker 2 Names:
The speaker developed strong, well-supported arguments and successfully Rebutted opponents arguments if applicable	10/9		
The speaker developed well-supported arguments and quite successfully rebutted opponents arguments if applicable	8/7		
The speaker developed satisfactory arguments, competently supported, and rebutted a number of the opponents arguments if applicable	6/5		
The speaker developed weak, poorly supported arguments and tried generally unsuccessfully to rebut opponents arguments if applicable	4/5		
The speaker developed largely irrelevant arguments and rebutted none of the opponents arguments if applicable	2/1		

Conclusion

The teachers should remember these things about speaking assessment:

1. Choose tasks that generate positive wash-back for teaching and learning

Select speaking assessment tasks that have a positive effect on the teaching and learning process. These tasks should be authentic as possible.

2. Allow time for a warm-up.

A warm-up will probably improve results. Speaking tests can be traumatic for second language learners. Use the warm-up activity to put students at ease.

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